

Standard Prompt for Usability Analysis Based on ISO 9241-210

This command directed the GAs to provide a more detailed and standardized analysis, focusing on the three main issues of ISO 9241-210: Effectiveness (delivering conference information and engaging users); Efficiency (time/effort required for navigation and information retrieval); and Satisfaction (users' subjective experience regarding ease of use, content clarity, and overall platform experience). In addition, the GAs were instructed to directly compare the COP30 and COP29 websites, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of each, their similarities and significant differences, and offering recommendations for improving the COP30 website:

“Make a detailed usability analysis of the website COP30 (URL: <https://cop30.br/en>) based on the requirements of the ISO 9241-210 standard, which addresses effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction. The analysis should include specific evaluations on:

- *Effectiveness: ability to fulfill objectives;*
- *Efficiency: time and effort required to accomplish tasks;*
- *Satisfaction: subjective perception of the user;*
- *Related heuristics.*

Repeat the same analysis for the website COP29 (URL: <https://cop29.az/en>).

Then, directly compare the usability of the two sites, highlighting:

- *Strengths and weaknesses of each;*
- *Significant similarities and differences;*
- *Concrete recommendations for improvements to the COP30 site, considering the context of a global audience engaged in climate change.*

Format the answer in three clear sections: Analysis of COP30, Analysis of COP29, and Comparison and Recommendations.”